

14th December, 1971

Dear Mr. Phillips,

Your letter dated 8th December addressed to my Son, Andrew, has been received. He is in America at the present time and I am not expecting him back until towards the end of the year. This, therefore, will explain the delay in your receiving a reply from him.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in dark ink, consisting of several overlapping loops and a trailing flourish, positioned above the typed name.

G.I. Williamson

David Phillips

Ollaberry
Grimms Hill
Great Missenden
Buckinghamshire
England